

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D3.3 Final Report on VITAL-5G integrated system and operational readiness results

Document Summary Information

Start Date	01/01/2021	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.vital5g.eu		
Deliverable	D3.3 Report on VITAL-5G integrated system and operational readiness results		
Related Work Package	WP3	Related Tasks	T3.2, T3.3
Contractual due date	30/06/2023	Actual submission date	30/06/2023
Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101016567

Contributors and Peer Reviewers

Contributors

Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christina Lessi (OTE), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Marius Iordache (ORO), Catalin Brezeanu (ORO), Oana Badita (ORO), Cosmin Schioapa (ORO), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA), George Suci (BEIA), Alex Vulpe (BEIA), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA)

Peer Reviewers

Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	13/4/2023	3%	Initial ToC and assignments	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)
V0.2	02/05/2023	25%	Initial contributions from partners	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christina Lessi (OTE), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Marius Iordache (ORO), Catalin Brezeanu (ORO), Oana Badita (ORO), Cosmin Schioapa (ORO), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA), George Suci (BEIA), Alex Vulpe (BEIA), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA)
V0.4	07/05/2023	40%	Review by editor and additional contributions + second round assignments	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)
V0.6	24/05/2023	65%	Second round of contributions	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christina Lessi (OTE), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier

				(IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Marius Iordache (ORO), Catalin Brezeanu (ORO), Oana Badita (ORO), Cosmin Schioapa (ORO), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA), George Suci (BEIA), Alex Vulpe (BEIA), Makis Stamatelatos (DIA)
V0.8	16/06/2023	80%	Preparation of version for peer review	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)
V0.85	22/06/2023	85%	First round of comments from peer reviewers	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)
V0.9	28/06/2023	90%	Final version ready for final review	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)
V0.95	29/06/2023	95%	Final review by project coordinator	Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS)
V1.0	30/06/2023	100%	Submission by project coordinator	Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS)

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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations Used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMC	Autonomic Management and Control
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AN	Autonomous Networks
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
CACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CB	Context Blueprint
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CNF	Container-based virtual Functions
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create/Read/Update/Delete
CTXBs	Context Blueprints
DE	Decision-making-Element
DEV	Development
DNS	Domain Name System
E2E	End to End
EC	European Commission
ELCM	Experiment Life-Cycle Manager
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute

EXPBs	Experiment Blueprints
EXPDs	Experiment Descriptors
Exp_ID	Experiment ID
GANA	Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture
gNB	gNodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Association
GST	Global Slice Template
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCI	Hyper Converged Infrastructure
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HW	Hardware
ID	Identification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
INT	Interoperability Testing
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
IWF	Interworking Framework
K8s	Kubernetes
KNF	Kubernetes-based Network Function
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LCM	LifeCycle Management
M2M	Machine to Machine
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
mIoT	Massive IoT
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNOs	Mobile Network Operators

MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
NAB	Network Application Blueprint
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NetOps	Network Operations
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	NFV Infrastructure
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NIC	Network Interface Card
NR	New Radio
NRF	NF Repository Function
NRS	Name Resolution Service
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptors
NSO	Network Services Orchestrator
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NSSI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
OAS	Open API Specification
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
ONAP	Open Networking Automation Platform
OS	Operating System
OSM	Open Source MANO
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PROD	Production
QoS	Quality Of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology

REST	Representational State Transfer
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
SA	Standalone
SB	Service Blueprint
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	South-Bound Interface
SCEF	Service Capability Exposure Function
SD	Slice Differentiator
SDN	Software Defined Radio
SEAL	Service Enabler Architecture Layer
SgNB	Secondary gNB
SINR	Signal to Interference & Noise Ratio
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SST	Slice/Service Type
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier
S-NSSAI	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance information
SW	Software
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TCB	Test Case Blueprint
TMV WG	Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
UE	User Equipment
UK	United Kingdom
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications

UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	VNF Descriptor
VNFM	VNF Manager
VS	Vertical Specific
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VxFs	Veritas File System
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

One of the primary objectives of the VITAL-5G project is to ensure that all the necessary upgrades and extensions are implemented across the three 5G testbeds and the vertical Transport & Logistics (T&L) infrastructures. These enhancements are crucial for conducting comprehensive VITAL-5G trials involving both internal users (consortium partners) and, more importantly, external 3rd-party experimenters.

To achieve this objective, detailed technical upgrades aligned with the 3GPP Rel.16 architecture have been outlined in D3.1 [6]. This document serves as a demonstration that, at the current stage, all hardware and software components required for the VITAL-5G centralized platform and the 5G testbeds (key elements as RAN, Core, Transport and Virtualization) have been successfully deployed, implemented, and integrated into an end-to-end functional scenario.

These implementations empower developers and experimenters, whether they belong to the consortium or external 3rd parties, to efficiently onboard, provision, run, and experiment with network applications on top of the enabled 5G infrastructure. The focus lies on enabling a robust and flexible environment for conducting trials, allowing for a wide range of innovative network applications to be tested and evaluated.

The VITAL-5G platform software components are implemented, on top of a dedicated virtualized infrastructure in the ORO testbed, in two flavours: **Development**, supporting the software components implementation, integration and testing activities, and the **Production** environment, the final VITAL-5G software components implementation. For clarity, the Production environment is based on the maturity of implementation of the components, after highly intensive tests performed in the Development area.

The validation is performed by using an integration and validation methodology that clearly certifies the successful platform components implementation, testing, validation and further integration with all the three testbeds, through the common platform infrastructure framework. The platform is deployed in high availability mode, as supported by the virtualized infrastructure in the ORO testbed, to guarantee the service continuity in case of any failures on some VMs or hardware issues.

This deliverable demonstrated that the three 5G testbeds have been successfully implemented according to the desired architecture, providing reliable 5G services to the end user experimenters. These testbeds have integrated and thoroughly tested the key components of the network, considering both the network functionality (such as RAN, Core, Transport, Virtualization, Orchestration, Monitoring Plugins) and the network service level. The evaluation process involves assessing the integration of hardware and software, as well as conducting end-to-end validation of the 5G standalone (SA) technology.

Importantly, all three testbeds have the capability to implement network slicing in the 5G SA environment. This means that they can establish distinct virtual networks with static configurations, allowing the provision of various communication services to end-users and network application developers. These services range from broadband connectivity to ultra-low-latency communication, catering to different requirements and use cases.

Throughout the experimentation activities conducted in these testbeds, a wide range of 5G SA capable devices have been successfully validated. This validation process enhances the overall capabilities of the testbeds, expanding their potential for experimentation and fostering opportunities for 3rd-party involvement. As a result, the experimentation path has been opened up to external entities who can now leverage these testbeds for their own innovative experiments and developments. A particularly relevant implementation has been achieved by providing the multi-slice availability by using a single 5G SA device with a single subscriber provisioning, with the proper slice being selected at the device level based on the traffic requirements through network and device configuration as described in D3.2 [7]. The deliverable not only proves the validation of the integrated system and operational readiness, based on the demonstrated results and outputs, but also validates the final VITAL-5G Platform features and 5G testbeds capabilities (e.g., Kubernetes integration in the three testbeds)

In addition to their successful deployment, the 5G testbeds have been seamlessly integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform in a secure manner. This integration has been achieved through the utilization of predefined interfaces specifically designed for slice management, monitoring, and services orchestration. By connecting with the VITAL-5G Platform, the testbeds enable a streamlined process for various activities, including network application onboarding, lifecycle management, monitoring, and experimental validation.

The **Production** VITAL-5G Platform serves as a centralized hub for managing these activities and facilitating interactions with each of the three testbeds. This is made possible through the implementation of dedicated plugins that are tailored to each testbed's requirements. These plugins provide the necessary functionalities for service and network monitoring, slice inventory management, and service orchestration within each respective testbed.

With the VITAL-5G Platform acting as the primary interface, network application developers and operators can leverage its capabilities to efficiently onboard their applications onto the testbeds. Furthermore, the platform supports the complete lifecycle management of these applications, ensuring smooth operations and continuous monitoring throughout the experimental process. This comprehensive approach allows for rigorous validation of the network applications' performance and functionality within the testbed environment.

Additionally, the VITAL-5G Platform serves as a bridge between the testbeds and the plugins dedicated to each one. This integration enables seamless communication and coordination between the platform and the testbeds, facilitating the exchange of data, commands, and instructions. The platform's plugins provide essential functionalities such as monitoring network services, managing slice inventories, and orchestrating services within the specific context of each individual testbed.

In summary, the integration between the 5G testbeds and the VITAL-5G Platform ensures a secure and efficient collaboration, enabling network application developers and operators to leverage the platform's capabilities for activities like onboarding, lifecycle management, monitoring, and experimental validation. The platform's plugins establish the necessary communication channels and provide specialized functionalities tailored to each testbed's requirements, ensuring seamless coordination and interaction between the platform and the testbeds.

1. Introduction

The integration and end-to-end (E2E) testing activities in the VITAL-5G project are divided into three distinct parts, integration activities in line with VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades and extensions [D3.1]. Each part focuses on specific integration aspects to ensure the seamless operation of the project components. The three parts include:

1. Integration of VITAL-5G Platform Software Components:

The first part revolves around integrating the software components of the VITAL-5G platform itself. This entails bringing together and harmonizing the various software elements that constitute the platform. Early in the project timeline, the core elements of the platform were integrated to form the initial release known as "Drop I." This release, which occurred around M15 (indicating the 15th month of the project), served as the foundation for subsequent integration and development efforts.

2. Integration of VITAL-5G Platform with the Three Testbeds:

The second part involves integrating the VITAL-5G Platform with the three designated testbeds. This integration ensures smooth interoperability and connectivity between the platform and the testbeds. By establishing a cohesive integration between the platform and the testbeds, the project aims to leverage the combined capabilities of both components to achieve comprehensive and reliable testing. This integration process encompasses the necessary configuration and communication setup between the platform and each individual testbed.

3. Internal Integration within Each Testbed:

The third part focuses on the internal integration within each of the three testbeds. This step entails integrating and aligning the internal components and functionalities within each testbed, ensuring they work harmoniously together. The objective is to establish a cohesive environment within each testbed, enabling efficient communication and coordination among the various components. This internal integration within the testbeds enhances their overall performance and supports the successful execution of experiments and trials.

By systematically addressing these three integration aspects, the VITAL-5G project aims to ensure the effective collaboration and functionality of its key components. The early integration of the platform core elements sets the foundation for further development and integration efforts. The successful integration between the VITAL-5G Platform and the three testbeds allows for comprehensive testing and experimentation, while the internal integration within each testbed ensures a cohesive and efficient operational environment.

The second release of the VITAL-5G platform i.e., Drop II released in deliverable D2.3 [3], is the first release fully integrated with the three testbeds' management functions for the monitoring, slicing and orchestration, thus enabling a complete and totally functional system which can be used for trials within the consortium or for 3rd party experiments. This release of the VITAL-5G system also includes the internal integrations of each testbed i.e., the 5G Core integration and the management functions integration with the lower parts of each one of the testbeds. The 2nd full release of the VITAL-5G platform, i.e., Drop III is released in M30 and thoroughly described in deliverable D2.4 [4].

Regarding the integration planning, this was organized into the splitting of the main workflow functions of the system, i.e., the Network Application Package onboarding, the Vertical Service instantiation and the Experiment creation, execution and monitoring, into weekly Sprints of work to better organize the timing and order of the integration process. The detailed planning includes the integration of the VITAL-5G platform with the northbound interfaces of the testbeds mediated by the per-testbed plugins for service orchestration, network slice management and network/service monitoring.

All the main workflows are integrated both at platform level and at the northbound interface level with the testbeds forming a complete system, ready for the 3rd parties' experimenters to start experimenting with the

platform. The internal testbed integrations are ready and validated, all of them offering 3GPP Rel. 16 5G connectivity with slicing and monitoring support. The orchestration management functions are integrated with the underlying virtualization infrastructures of each testbed and the southbound interfaces of the centrally located platform in Orange Romania. The monitoring and slicing management functions of all testbeds are also integrated with the platform and the underlying infrastructure of each testbed.

The development and testing phases of the VITAL-5G platform and testbeds were planned around three distinct phases, named Drop I, II and III. Each Drop has different targets for component integration and testing, and it derives from the software development plan defined in WP2 and initially reported in D2.1 [2]. This plan specifies the components available in each software release of the VITAL-5G platform and its functionalities, providing high level guidelines for the list of modules and features to be integrated in each drop. Moreover, the integration plan has been built on the basis of the components' interfaces and the general workflows for Network Application Package Onboarding, Vertical Service Instantiation and Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring, as described in deliverables D1.2 [1], D2.1 [2], D2.3 [3] and D2.4 [4].

For clarity of integration results and achievements, the reader should first get acquainted with the D1.2 [1], D2.1 [2] and D2.3 [3] deliverables, where the architecture, workflows, component implementation specifics, functionality and interfaces between components are described. This deliverable will serve as a guide on how the integration methodology was implemented up to the release of Drop III of the VITAL-5G platform, how the Network Applications (Network Applications) were onboarded and how the Vertical Services can be instantiated followed by a description on how the user will be able to create, execute and monitor an experiment. The deliverable offers a concise description of the northbound interfaces of the testbeds (Belgian, Romanian and Greek), as well as the associated plugins.

The successful implementation of the components is demonstrated in this deliverable through a series of relevant outputs from the 5G testbeds or VITAL-5G components, outputs that are proving our full networks and services implementation.

1.1. Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 3.2 VITAL-5G system components integration	The VITAL-5G experimentation facility is a multi-component structure comprised of existing, upgraded 5G testbeds (T3.1), vertical facilities and equipment (T3.1), open virtual platform and repository (T2.2) and Network Applications (T2.1) and vertical intelligent applications (T2.4), which are all developed in different tasks. This task will be responsible for the end-to-end integration of all these heterogeneous components into one single, smoothly functioning system, guaranteeing the interoperability and cooperation of the different HW and SW elements and delivering a functional experimentation facility.	Section 3. Integration Status	Describes the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform with respect to the three testbeds.
		Section 4. Common Platform Infrastructure	Describes the common platform infrastructure status for running the VITAL-5G platform.
		Section 5. Testbed Components Integration and Testing	Describes the integration between the testbed components with particular emphasis to the standalone 5G Cores, orchestration and management.
		Section 6. Platform and Testbed Integration	Describes the integration of the testbeds with the VITAL-5G platform.
Task 3.3 VITAL-5G platform functional testing and operational readiness	The aim of this task is to conduct preliminary functional acceptance tests to assess the performance of the VITAL-5G Platform and technically validate its proper operation including the 5G network infrastructure, so as to reduce the ambiguities prior to field trial use case validation. These initial trials will perform functional testing on each of the Platform's components to ensure that they are operationally ready for the trials. Dry runs will be performed to benchmark	Section 4. First full-release of the VITAL-5G platform is operational in production environment	Describes the VITAL-5G Platform deployment in the VMs installed in production environment

	<p>the performance of the system against target network and application-level KPIs. The intention is to achieve a fully functional Platform providing an environment suitable for Network Applications and use case testing and validation</p>		
DELIVERABLE			
D3.3 Report on VITAL-5G integrated system & operational readiness results.			

1.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is split into the following sections:

- Section 2 describes the platform component status and their availability to the production system.
- Section 3 describes the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform with the three testbeds at M30.
- Section 4 describes the common platform virtual infrastructure status for running the centralized VITAL-5G platform deployed in ORO testbed at M30.
- Section 5 describes the integration between the testbed components with particular emphasis to the standalone 5G Cores, the orchestration of each testbed and its integration with the virtualized environments.
- Section 6 describes the 3rd party onboarding activities and the testbed resources available for the onboarded experimenters as well as the KPIs achieved and future planning of our activities.

Finally, the document concludes with the summary of the results presented in this deliverable.

2. Platform Component Status

The platform component status is shown in Table 1 and describes the VITAL-5G components status and their production deployment status as of the date of submission of this deliverable. In this chapter, we describe the general Architecture components status, starting with the software component of the Portal Web GUI to the component for Multi-Slice Inventory, as presented.

The VITAL-5G platform components are fully implemented, tested and validate (including the interworking with the three testbeds), as demonstrated by the VITAL-5G availability in the production environment, through which all the validation tests have been performed. The overall functionality and detailed description of each one of the components is detailed in D2.1 [2] and the set of features available on the second full release (**M30**) is described in D2.4 [4], concluding the successful platform components integration, as per details presented in Annex I: Integration Plan, the status flow of the Integration Plan and the sprint analysis of the following: Network Application Package Onboarding, Vertical Services Instantiation, Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring, and the Delivery Plans for testbed northbound interface and adaptation plugins.

Table 1: Platform Component Status at M30.

Architecture Component	SW Components	Completion Status	Responsible Partner	Production
Portal Web GUI	Portal Web GUI	100%	eBOS	Yes
Network Application Catalogue	Network Applications, Services and Experiment Catalogue	100%	NXW	Yes
Service Catalogue				
Experiment Catalogue				
Vertical Services LCM	Service LCM	100%	NXW	Yes
Network Application Validator	Network Application Validator	100%	BEIA	Yes
Blueprint Validation Tool				
Service Testing & Experiment Manager	Experiment LCM	100%	NXW	Yes
	Intent-based Requests Manager	100%	BEIA/NXW	Yes
Result Analytics	Result Analytics	100%	WINGS	Yes
AI-based Diagnostics	AI-based Diagnostics	100%	WINGS	Yes
Service & Network Monitoring	Centralized Monitoring Platform	100%	IMEC	Yes

Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory	Slice Manager	100%	IMEC	Yes
Multi-site Inventory	Multi-site Inventory	100%	NXW	Yes
Licence Manager	Licence Manager	100%	NXW	Yes
ML/Analytics Toolkit	ML/Analytics Toolkit	100%	INCE	Yes

3. Integration and Testing Status

The development and testing phase were designed around three distinct phases, as presented, named Drop I, II and III. Each Drop has different targets for component integration and testing, following the software development plan described in D2.1 [2] for the VITAL-5G platform. Each Drop is defined by the components to be integrated as well as the general workflows described in the relevant architecture deliverables. This section describes the integration and testing methodology and the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform at **M30**.

The integration and testing methodology employed throughout these phases aims to ensure the integration and functionality of the VITAL-5G platform. This methodology includes a systematic approach to component integration and comprehensive testing procedures. By following this methodology, the project team can assess the readiness and performance of the platform while identifying and addressing any potential issues.

As of M30 (June 2023), the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform is described. This assessment provides an overview of the progress made in finally validating the integration of various components and the overall status of the platform's integration. It serves as a snapshot of the platform's capabilities and its alignment with the project's timeline and objectives.

The integration and testing methodology, along with the integration status at M30, are crucial aspects of the development and testing phase in the VITAL-5G project. They ensure a structured approach to component integration and testing, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the platform's performance. This information helps in tracking the progress of the project and providing insights into the current status of the VITAL-5G platform, all integration and validation activities and results being internally tracked.

3.1. End to End Integration and Testing Methodology

In order to optimise the E2E integration and testing of the platform and testbeds, based on lessons learned from D3.2 [7], we have established better communication between WP2 and WP3 in order to hold the minimum number of meetings with maximum efficiency per meeting in mind.

The Testbed Level Status Dashboards are exclusively deduced from the Workflow Level Status Dashboard Sprints and they give a detailed status of each testbed. These Dashboards monitor the work in a very detailed manner, including the testbed plugins required to integrate each testbed with the VITAL-5G Platform. The Dashboards are designed in such a way to be able to add specific testbed sprints and dive into the testbed specific parts, i.e., internal testbed integration efforts.

The Overall Workflows Delivery Plan represents the overall integration status of the project, i.e., the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform and the three testbeds. It is deduced from the Workflow Status Dashboards and the Testbed Status Dashboards.

The VITAL-5G Components and Infrastructure status has a description of the status of all platform components, testbed infrastructure and plugins and it is loosely coupled with the Workflow Level Status Dashboards, in the sense that the sprint reporting should be compatible with the development status of the actual components and vice versa.

3.2. Platform Status at M30

By M30 (June 2023), significant progress has been made in the development of the VITAL-5G platform, and it is now fully operational in the targeted release. Drop III, the final phase of updates to the platform, focuses on optimizing the Quality of Experience (QoE) for 3rd-party experimenters. Several key enhancements have been implemented to achieve this goal:

License Manager: A license manager has been incorporated into the platform, providing crucial information about the implementation of Network Applications. This feature assists 3rd-party users in tailoring their specific requirements and needs to the available Network Application catalog.

ML/Analytics Component: A machine learning and analytics component has been added to the platform, enabling advanced data post-processing capabilities. This component leverages the insights derived from the previously implemented VA3 Network Application, enhancing the platform's analytical capabilities.

Automated Closed-Loop Workflows: The platform now supports automated closed-loop workflows, enabling automated lifecycle management actions. This feature streamlines the management of Network Applications, allowing for more efficient operations and improved performance.

Furthermore, various minor improvements have been implemented across other components of the platform. These enhancements, described in detail in deliverable D2.4 [4], contribute to overall performance and usability.

With the platform fully operational, it has been actively utilized by 3rd-party experimenters who have successfully been identified and onboarded onto the platform. These external users are actively engaging with the platform, conducting experiments and providing valuable feedback.

Moving forward, the project team aims to collect and incorporate feedback from these 3rd-party experimenters to further refine and improve the platform. This iterative process of gathering feedback and implementing improvements will continue until the end of the project, with the intention of extending the platform's enhancements even beyond the project's completion.

In summary, at M30, the VITAL-5G platform is fully operational and has undergone significant updates during Drop III. At M30 (June 2023), the VITAL-5G platform is fully operational and Drop III features the last updates to the platform optimizing Quality of Experience for 3rd party experimenters by implementing a licence manager that provides information concerning the implementation of Network Applications that helps 3rd-party users tailor their needs to our Network Application catalogue, an ML/Analytics component that provides data post-processing capabilities derived from the previously implemented VA3 Network Application and support of automated closed-loop workflows to enable automated lifecycle management actions. Several minor improvements have been implemented in other components which are described in detail in deliverable D2.4 [4].

The platform is now actively used by 3rd party experimenters that have been identified and onboarded to the platform. The next steps until the end of the project is to gather the feedback from these individuals and continue improving the platform until the project end and beyond for as long as possible.

4. Drop 3 Common Platform Infrastructure

The VITAL-5G Platform is the entry point offering the VITAL-5G service design, and experimentation services on top of the infrastructure of the three 5G enabled testbeds of the project. As described in D1.2 [1] (and further evolved in D1.3 [2]), this platform enables:

- **Network Application and Vertical Service Design and Management:** The platform offers a catalogue of Network Applications and vertical services. Users can onboard these applications and potentially share them with others, with automated management of the orchestration descriptors. This streamlines the process of designing and managing network applications and services within the platform.
- **Automated Monitoring Configuration, Data Retrieval, and Visualization:** The platform leverages metrics described in network application and vertical service blueprints to automatically configure monitoring settings. It extracts relevant metrics from the testbed, ensuring comprehensive monitoring of the platform. The collected data can then be visualized, providing valuable insights into the performance and behavior of the deployed services.
- **5G Network Slice Management Capabilities:** The platform includes a 5G slice catalogue and offers lifecycle management capabilities for 5G slices. It utilizes the 5G slice profile and characteristics to allocate a suitable 5G slice to a service. Additionally, the platform can dynamically create slices based on the requirements of the testbed, ensuring efficient resource allocation and management.
- **Experiment Execution and Report Generation Support:** The VITAL-5G platform facilitates the execution of experiments and provides support for generating experiment reports. Users can validate experiment Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through the Portal Web GUI, enabling comprehensive evaluation and analysis of the conducted experiments.
- **AI-based Service Troubleshooting:** The platform incorporates an AI-based analytics module, enabling automated service analysis using AI algorithms. This functionality enhances the experiment reports and assists in identifying and troubleshooting issues. By leveraging AI, the platform can provide valuable insights and support automated closed-control loop actions to optimize service performance.
- **ML/Analytics Toolkit for Data Postprocessing:** The VITAL-5G platform offers machine learning (ML) and analytics capabilities for data postprocessing. These capabilities aim to identify abnormal or outlier behavior in the monitored KPIs. By applying ML techniques to analyse service data, the platform enhances anomaly detection and provides valuable insights for further analysis and optimization.
- **Automated Service Lifecycle Management Capabilities:** The platform automates the lifecycle management of network services associated with Network Applications. This includes the validation of available licenses, ensuring the appropriate licensing for services. The automated management streamlines the lifecycle processes and ensures efficient utilization of resources.

As described in D2.1 [2] and evolved in D2.2 [5], D2.3 [3] and the final WP2 deliverable, D2.4 [4] that describes the final (Drop III) version the VITAL-5G Platform is composed by a set of components interacting most of the times through REST-based interface, to provide a specific set of functionalities.

4.1. Comparison Between Drop 2 and Drop 3

The components mentioned in the previous section have either been completely new and developed within the VITAL-5G project or reused based on previous projects and evolved during the project's lifetime. Furthermore, minor, major and/or final releases have been described in previous deliverables. At Drop III as an update of Drop II, the VITAL-5G platform features:

- A Licence Manager that is responsible for: (i) Storing and managing the licenses associated with the Network Applications; (ii) Keep an updated status of the usage of the Network Application licenses; (iii)

- Validate the Network Application and Vertical Service lifecycle management operations (e.g., Instantiation requests).
- An ML/Analytics component that offers AI/ML capabilities for service data post processing, which aims to identify outlying behaviour/abnormal data with respect to monitored KPIs. The functionality was originally developed in the context of VA3 Network Application, however it was decided to be integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform in order to complement the existing analytics and AI features and allow for a horizontal to the project impact, as it will allow the user to process the results of the experiments and train their own models and acquire results with zero code.
 - At the VITAL-5G GUI level we provided additional support tools for 3rd party users including templates for uploading Vertical Services Instances with as little trouble as possible. One of the tools is the Network Application validator, released with the final operational version of the platform, that allows users to run checks in their 3rd party Network Application before uploading it on the platform. In addition, various QoE improvements have been implemented such as more intuitive and user-friendly access to the Monitoring Panels and Service Instantiation.
 - The Service LCM supports vertical service scaling/modification for closed-loop automation through the implementation of REST-based interfaces (used by other platform modules) and logic to enable automated service scaling.
 - The Network Application and Blueprint Validation tool features experiment termination as part of the Network Application instantiation and experiment lifecycle workflow as well as integration with the Access Control component.
 - At Drop III an intent-based Requests Manager that provides an alternative mechanism to define VITAL-5G experiments, adopting an approach based on the natural language. It supports two mechanisms that help the experimenters to express their intentions. One is based on free text, where experimenters can write a sentence to describe the characteristics of the desired experiment. The description is then automatically translated by the module into a blueprint. The second mechanism is based on guided selection and filling of the fields that defines an experiment, through a set of web pages that guides the experimenter during the entire procedure. Interaction between the experiment LCM and the intent-based manager is enabled such that it can trigger experiments in the facility where the Network Applications are deployed/onboarded. The intent-based Requests Manager is also successfully integrated with the Access Control module.
 - One of the key features introduced in Drop III of the VITAL-5G Platform is the support of **automated closed-loop workflows** to enable automated lifecycle management actions upon detection of a certain monitoring condition or the firing of a diagnostic event. As detailed in D2.4 [4], the Service LCM, internally configures the events/metrics to monitor, and subscribing to the correspondent topics through the API of the Service & Network Monitoring. In the case of Network service scaling, the Service LCM uses OSM primitives to trigger the scaling procedure, as shown in D2.4. In the case of Network Slice modification, the Service LCM uses the API exposed the multi-site 5G Slice Manager and Inventory. Depending on the testbed capabilities, the network slice modification is performed by either creating/deploying a new slice or reconfiguring the existing one, thereby enabling the fulfilment of requirements of vertical services that are associated with the slices. The 5G Slice Manager and Inventory component is in charge of processing this modification request, which is further sending corresponding requests to slice plugins installed on the VITAL-5G testbeds.

5. End-to-End testing and validation of 5G testbeds

The 5G SA testbed's components integration and testing status is described in Table 2 and finally demonstrated in the specific testbed's chapters, following the plans and upgrades to the target architecture described in D3.1 [6]. The testbeds are enabled to support the VITAL-5G E2E services orchestration and experimentation activities, successful validation being achieved not only for component integration perspective but also being demonstrated at the service level:

- Network Application Onboarding (Services instantiation and visualization)
- Service LCM – 5G slicing
- Service monitoring

In all three testbeds, we have upgraded the OSM to version 12 in order to avoid a series of orchestration bugs identified with the previous version (OSM R10) during the integration processes and workflows, experimented upon using continuously the VITAL-5G platform on the testbeds. The summary presented in the table is highlighting the actual 5G SA testbed components status for the 5G Hardware (HW) and Software (SW) integration and end-to-end (E2E) 5G services, the 5G RAN and Core in VITAL-5G testbeds are following the targeted 3GPP Rel.16.

Table 2: VITAL-5G testbed components integration and testing status.

Testbed	Status HW/SW (%) 3GPP Rel16	RAN gNB	5GCN Comp.	Transport network	Slicing eMBB/URLLC	Orchestration OSMv12	Monitoring Internal Probes
Antwerp	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
Bucharest	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
Greek	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%

5.1. Testbeds Integration and E2E testing

The VITAL-5G Platform is integrated with the 5G Testbeds through specific interfaces for the (1) Monitoring system, (2) 5G Slice Management System and (3) NFV MANO System, as described in D3.1 [5]. The detailed unified interfaces towards the VITAL-5G Platform (Drop III) are presented in D2.4 [3] for monitoring and slice management, while the interface with the NFV MANO system is based on the standard ETSI SOL interfaces already supported by OSM. For each testbed, the relevant plugins have been developed to handle the translation

with the interfaces supported by the tools and platforms deployed in each testbed, as presented in detail in Table 3 and Figure 1.

Table 3: VITAL-5G Platform and Testbed Integration status.

VITAL-5G Interfaces/Testbed	Service & Network monitoring plugin	Multi-slice inventory and management plugin	Service orchestration plugin
Antwerp	100%	100%	100%
Bucharest	100%	100%	100%
Greek	100%	100%	100%

Figure 1: VITAL-5G Platform and testbed design and integration.

5.2. Platform and Belgian Testbed Integration

At the Belgian 5G testbed side, we have successfully finalized the integration activities for the M30 milestone. In particular, the integration tests included: the onboarding, deploying, and instantiation of both the Network Applications and the vertical services, network/service/platform/infrastructure monitoring, and static slice management.

5.2.1. Network Application onboarding and vertical instantiation

Concerning the onboarding and vertical service deployment activities, we successfully onboarded and deployed the entire vertical service 1, i.e., “Remote vessel monitoring”, which belongs to the UC1 within the Antwerp trial site, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. The remote vessel monitoring vertical service consists of the following Network Applications: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II (VS8), Monitoring dashboard (VS5), and Real-time digital twin (VA5). Real-time metrics coming from the Antwerp testbed can also be collected.

Below are the steps that we took in order to onboard, deploy, and instantiate the above-mentioned remote vessel monitoring vertical service, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. All integration activities were performed using both OSM versions 10 and 12.

First, we successfully onboarded the three Network Applications, which compose our remote vessel monitoring vertical service, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI (Figure 87). This step involved uploading the correct zip file of the onboarded Network Application and also the proper VNF Descriptors (VNFDs) that correspond to Network Applications in the vertical service, as well as the Network Service Descriptors (NSDs) of the entire vertical service.

Id	Name	Testbed	Version	Software Documentation
7aa05554-55b1-4d7f-add3-fda372d4cbe4	Seafar/IMEC On Board Data Collection	ANTWERP1.0		
b9334759-29e1-437c-b99e-05365f2ea447	IMEC Real Time Digital Twin	ANTWERP1.0		
6d663cb8-f85c-471d-946d-ed24e9a69f82	Seafar Remote Vessel Monitoring	ANTWERP1.0		

Figure 2: Onboarding blueprints of Network Applications in the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI; Network Applications used in this example are building the Remote vessel monitoring vertical service.

After a successful blueprint onboarding, the Network Application blueprints are displayed in the Antwerp local OSM, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The onboarded Net Applications are available on the Antwerp local OSM.

The next step is to onboard and instantiate the remote vessel monitoring vertical service on the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. This step has been performed by uploading the NSD of vertical service 1 through the Portal Web GUI, and the outcome is showcased in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Successfully instantiated the remote vessel monitoring vertical service through the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI.

The result of the successful deployment of the vertical service instance (i.e., remote vessel monitoring vertical service) using the local OSM deployment is shown in Figure 5. Finally, the deployed instance of the remote vessel monitoring vertical service is spawned up on top of the local OpenStack, where all Network Applications are running as VM instances in the OpenStack environment (Figure 6). Thus, all Network Applications that compose the vertical service for remote vessel monitoring are up and running in the OpenStack environment as VMs. They are attached to the proper pre-configured OpenStack network in order to be able to communicate with each other.

Figure 7: A real-time influx of network latency in the Belgian 5G testbed.

Figure 8: A real-time influx of CPU load in the Belgian 5G testbed.

Figure 9: A real-time influx of the service metric “Dangerous Object Count” in the Belgian 5G testbed.

5.2.3. Network slicing

As one of the integration activities, static network slicing and interfacing between the slice plugin on the Belgian 5G testbed and the slice inventory on the VITAL-5G platform have been developed and tested. The capabilities that have been tested in this release and integration phase are limited to real-time reporting of slice profiles available in the 5G network on the Belgian testbed (Figure 10). These activities include the very first report on the preconfigured network slices (both URLLC and eMBB) so that the slice inventory component can store those profiles in the database, and use the available information when deciding where to deploy a particular vertical service, and to which slice to attach the corresponding user.

Besides the activities of reporting the profiles of the preconfigured network slices, in this phase we have also managed to test updating an existing slice based on the manual change of slice parameters (Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13), and the deletion of preconfigured network slices. In the next integration phase, the complete performance of slicing capabilities and slice plugin will be tested, including the interaction between Service LCM and Slice inventory, which results in certain dynamic changes in the slice profiles on the 5G testbed.

```

2022-12-16 09:59:24.130 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] b.i.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Successfully stored the new slice with ID: AntwerpUrllc01 of the site: antwerp
2022-12-16 10:00:43.136 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-3] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully stored the new slice with ID: AntwerpEmbb01 of the site: antwerp
2022-12-16 10:02:36.358 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-5] b.i.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Successfully updated the Urllc slice for: AntwerpUrllc01
2022-12-16 10:03:48.058 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully updated the slice with ID: AntwerpEmbb01
2022-12-16 10:04:25.692 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-8] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully delete the slice: AntwerpEmbb01
    
```

Figure 10: The report on the successful action of storing slice-related information in the Slice inventory database.

```

sliceinventory=# select * from embb_slice;
 id | area_traffic_capdl | area_traffic_capul | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | site | slice_id | traffic_type | user_density | user_speed
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          200 |          200 |          200 |          200 | Antwerp | AntwerpEmbb01 | UDP |          |          200 |          80
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from embb_slice_imsi;
 embb_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
              1 | imsi1
              1 | imsi2
              1 | imsi3
              1 | imsi4
(4 rows)
    
```

Figure 11: The details of the eMBB slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          100 |          100 |      1 |         16 | Antwerp | AntwerpUrllc01 | UDP
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
              1 | imsi1
              1 | imsi2
              1 | imsi3
              1 | imsi4
(4 rows)
    
```

Figure 12: The details of the URLLC slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          100 |          100 |      1 |         14 | antwerp | AntwerpUrllc01 | TCP
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
              1 | imsi1
              1 | imsi2
              1 | imsi3
(3 rows)
    
```

Figure 13: The details of the updated URLLC slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

5.3. Platform and Romanian Testbed Integration

The Romanian testbed is fully integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform for LCM Interface, Monitoring and Slice interfaces, using the plugins developed by ORO for VITAL-5G Platform interactions, as described below.

5.3.1. Network application onboarding and vertical instantiation

The service orchestration plugin is embedded in the SOL006 NBI of the Romanian testbed orchestrator, directly connected to the VITAL-5G Platform. The testing of deployment and other lifecycle management actions triggered by the VITAL-5G Platform is successful on OSM, as described in the following examples.

Figure 14: Romanian testbed Network Applications successful instantiation status message.

Figure 15: Romanian testbed visualisation at OSM level.

Figure 16: Romanian testbed visualisation at Openstack level.

5.3.2. Monitoring

The Monitoring Plugin in the Romanian testbed is an application built in python using Flask Web framework and following the high-level architecture represented in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Romanian testbed monitoring plugin architecture.

```

VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:13.714091Z", "value": 0.21385416666666662, "unit": "%", "vmId": 541}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
latency
galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:13.141039Z", "value": "4", "unit": "ms", "networksSliceId": 20}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
CPU_LOAD
va_vm
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:23.869685Z", "value": 0.21385416666666662, "unit": "%", "vmId": 541}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
latency
galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:23.302060Z", "value": "3", "unit": "ms", "networksSliceId": 20}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
CPU_LOAD
va_vm
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:34.006853Z", "value": 0.21385416666666662, "unit": "%", "vmId": 541}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
latency
galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:34.458717Z", "value": "4", "unit": "ms", "networksSliceId": 20}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
CPU_LOAD
va_vm
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:44.151428Z", "value": 0.21385416666666662, "unit": "%", "vmId": 541}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
latency
galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:44.614433Z", "value": "2", "unit": "ms", "networksSliceId": 20}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
CPU_LOAD
va_vm
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:54.293841Z", "value": 0.21385416666666662, "unit": "%", "vmId": 541}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-infrastructure-CPU_LOAD
latency
galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency
in screen
{"timestamp": "2023-03-15T14:37:54.752076Z", "value": "4", "unit": "ms", "networksSliceId": 20}
<Class_str>
VSI04cd809be-3165-4f7a-a5d3-de5d0be34ab9-galati-network-latency

```

Figure 18: Romanian testbed's plugin's functionality.

It is used to translate the specific metrics requested from the VITAL-5G Centralised Monitoring Platform and to expose them on a dedicated queue and port that is correlated to the type of resource that is necessary to be monitored and delivered. The plugin is available on the Git¹, through the network metrics publisher.

In the production environment, the plugin exposes two main API calls, as defined:

- localTestbed/galati
 - Used to start a collection of requested metrics using a specific process and topic, there will be produced values for metrics (start metric collection)
- localTestbed/stop/metric/publisher
- Used to stop the process for specific topics and metrics when requested by the Centralised Platform (stop metrics collection)

The Romanian testbed is able to collect and publish various metrics, as described in D4.1 [8] (CPU Load, RAM, Latency, Network), some examples as seen in Figure 19, Figure 20 .

¹ <https://gitlab.com/vital-5g>

Figure 19: Romanian testbed monitoring infrastructure CPU monitoring.

Figure 20: Romanian testbed monitoring End-to-End slice Latency monitoring.

5.3.3. Network slicing

Slice Plugin RO 5G SA is a python application that is using the Flask Web framework and it is working as a proxy for the Slice Inventory component of the VITAL-5G project infrastructure. This plugin ensures that the centralised VITAL-5G Slicing management component is able to obtain or modify information about users and slices as described in D2.4 [4].

Figure 21: Romanian testbed VITAL-5G Slice Platform configuration.

At this milestone, the Slice Plugin is developed using three main components, as described below, adapting the Romanian testbed capabilities to VITAL-5G platform APIs:

- retrieve data about a specific slice and slice users (using a GET API call), translating the VITAL-5G platform call request into specific testbed API call

Example of Testbed API call for slice inventory, following testbed APIs existing Southbound Interfaces, results presented at the VITAL-5G Platform level:

GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles

Results are described by the next figure, highlighting the variety of slice profiles in the testbed.

```

2023-03-15 14:31:14.577 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Needs to select this slice requirements: SelectSliceUrllc(latency=10.0, jitter=1.0, expDataRateDL=40.0, expDataRateUL=40.0, testbed=galati, imsi=226107900000088)
2023-03-15 14:31:14.584 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : slices for galati testbeds: 3
2023-03-15 14:31:14.584 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : There are in total: 3 that match the requirement a random slice will be picked
2023-03-15 14:31:14.585 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.s.MultiSiteInventoryService : Sending GET request to: http://172.28.18.98:8084/multisite-inventory/GALATI/slicing
2023-03-15 14:31:14.599 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.s.MultiSiteInventoryService : Successfully retrieved the default slice configuration for the: galati testbed
2023-03-15 14:31:14.600 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] i.v.s.s.SlicePluginCommunicatorService : Contacting the local Slice Plugin of the testbed: GALATI to attach the slice Sending POST request to: http://172.28.22.181:8081/sliceUe/attach
2023-03-15 14:31:27.919 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] i.v.s.s.SlicePluginCommunicatorService : This has been sent: {"imsi": "226107900000088", "sliceId": "Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC", "usedDataRateDL": "40.0", "usedDataRateUL": "40.0"}
2023-03-15 14:31:27.919 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] i.v.s.s.SlicePluginCommunicatorService : The Slice Plugin on the GALATI successfully attached the slice.
2023-03-15 14:31:27.919 INFO 3267 --- [0.0-8080-exec-4] b.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Successfully attached the imsi to the selected (urllc) slice with slice id: Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC
vital@vital5g-slice-inventory-DEV: ~/vincent/sliceInventory/version-5/sliceInventory$
    
```

Figure 22: Romanian testbed slice inventory output.

Example of Testbed API call for slice profile, in this example an uRLLC slice descriptor, as seen in Figure 21.

GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles/eMBB2

```
sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
id | exp_data_rate_d | exp_data_rate_u | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
1 | 1000 | 1000 | 1 | 10 | galati | Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC | critical
(1 row)
```

Figure 23: Romanian testbed eMBB2 slice configuration.

Example of Testbed API call for subscriber slice profile, as seen in Figure 106 GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1//uiccs/<subscriber-ID>.

```
sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
1 | 22610790000077
(1 row)
```

Figure 24: Romanian testbed subscriber attached to slice (eMBB).

- Attach or override a specific subscriber to a slice, (using a POST API call), translating the VITAL-5G platform call request into specific testbed API call
- PUT https://https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/<subscriber name>' -T add_sub_with_PUT.json -H "Content-Type: application/json" Remove a specific subscriber
- DELETE 'https://APC-IP:<port>apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/<Subscriber name>'

Figure 25: Romanian testbed Core Network 5G Slicing configuration.

5.4. Platform and Greek Testbed Integration

The Greek testbed is fully integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform for LCM Interface, Monitoring and Slice interfaces, using the plugins developed for VITAL-5G Platform interactions, as described below.

5.4.1. Network Applications onboarding

The Openstack instances created for the Network Services are shown below in Figure 26 and Figure 27. The ELCM-RAV integration instances are built using the same flavor: four vCores, 4GB of memory and 20GB of disk. WINGS' currently instantiated Network Application uses a basic flavor: one vCore, 1GB of memory and 10GB of disk. The network subnets configured are also shown. All instances created via OSM use the same SSH keypair for authentication.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State
<input type="checkbox"/>	elcm-rav-integra-1-HALVM-0	vital-hal10	192.168.1.83, 10.10.10.50	vital_fivr	vital	Active	nova	None	Running
<input type="checkbox"/>	elcm-rav-integra-2-msgbrokerVM-0	vital-msgbroker	192.168.1.236, 10.10.10.44	vital_fivr	vital	Active	nova	None	Running
<input type="checkbox"/>	elcm-rav-integra-3-storageVM-0	vital-dash	192.168.1.34, 10.10.10.48	vital_fivr	vital	Active	nova	None	Running
<input type="checkbox"/>	elcm-rav-integra-4-technicaldatavisualizationVM-0	vital-datavis	192.168.1.191, 10.10.10.25	vital_fivr	vital	Active	nova	None	Running

Figure 26: Example 1 of Openstack instances in the Greek testbed

<input type="checkbox"/>	Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State
<input type="checkbox"/>	VITAL-5G_WINGS_N-vnf-wings_vital-VM-0	vital_v4	datanet_V 192.168.2.103 mgmtnet_V 192.168.1.192, 10.10.10.34	hackfest_basic-VM-flv	vital	Active	nova	None	Running

Figure 27: Example 2 of Openstack instances in the Greek testbed

5.4.2. Monitoring Integration

The Greek Testbed Monitoring Plugin is an application built in Python using the Flask web framework and implements the architecture shown in Figure 26. The reader can refer to D3.2 [7] for more information.

Figure 28: Monitoring plugin architecture of the Greek testbed.

In the figures below, you can find examples of published metrics.

Figure 29: VITAL 5G -Athens’s testbed – RTT latencies

Figure 30: Grafana measurements on robot's Linear, Reverse & Angular Velocity

5.4.3. Slicing Integration

The slicing plugin of the Greek testbed, is an application build in Java and uses the Spring Boot Framework². It translates the southbound interface of the platform. The slice profiles for the URLLC and eMBB slices for all the VITAL-5G testbeds (including the Greek) can be seen in Figure 27 and Figure 28.

² <https://spring.io/>

```
sliceinventory=# SELECT * from urllc_slice;
```

id	exp_data_rate_d1	exp_data_rate_ul	jitter	latency	site	slice_id	traffic_type
1	100	100	1	14	antwerp	AntwerpUrllc01	TCP
2	100	100	1	14	beds	radutest	
3	1000	1000	1	10	galati	Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC	critical
4	1000	1000	1	10	galati	Galati_URLLC	critical
5	40	40	1	10	galati	Galati_URLLC-40M	critical
6	100	10	1	5	Athens	Vital-5G-Athens-URLLC1	TCP
7	100	10	1	7	Athens	Vital-5G-Athens-URLLC2	TCP

(7 rows)

Figure 31: URLLC slices profiles in all of the VITAL-5G testbeds.

id	area_traffic_cap_d1	area_traffic_cap_ul	exp_data_rate_d1	exp_data_rate_ul	site	slice_id	traffic_type	user_density	user_speed
1	200	200	200	200	antwerp	AntwerpEmbb01	TCP	200	80
2	10	10	1000	1000	galati	Galati_eMBB	broadband	200	80
3	10	10	100	100	galati	Galati_eMBB2	broadband	200	80
4	200	200	1000	1000	Athens	Vital-5G-Athens-EMBB1	UDP	200	80
5	200	200	1000	1000	Athens	Vital-5G-Athens-EMBB2	UDP	200	80

(5 rows)

Figure 32: eMBB slices profiles in all of the VITAL-5G testbeds.

It acts as a mediator between the 5G Core network and the VITAL-5G platform, implementing the commonly agreed slicing interface. During the period that these deliverable reporting covers, there has been an interface update and more specifically multiple IMSIs can be attached to a slice with a single operation, instead of only one.

5.4.4. Metrics

5.4.4.1. Network KPIs

The metric RTT - Round-trip time (RTT) is essential in networking that can indicate the quality of communications between two endpoints and is used for real-time performance monitoring.

Figure 33: VITAL 5G – Athens’s testbed – RTT latency (MQTT).

Figure 34: VITAL 5G – Athens’s testbed – RTT latency (ICMP).

Figure 35: VITAL 5G – Athens’s testbed – RTT latency (ICMP) Distribution..

- *Bandwidth & UL/DL data rate*
- *Network latency*
- *Packet loss*
 - 1) **Service KPIs:**
 - *Industrial task/operation completion time*
 - *Number of packages shipped/served/min/hour.*
 - *Number of incidents*
 - *Availability*
 - 2) **Infrastructure KPIs:**
 - *CPU*
 - *RAM*
 - *DISK*
 - *Battery level*
 - *Power consumption*

- *Location- (x, y)*

5.4.4.2. KPI results and reports

1) Services KPIs:

- **GR_SL_KPI_1:** Avg_Order Line_Pick_time: Average time duration to complete the picking of an order line. An order is comprised of multiple order lines. The number of order lines per order is variable.
- **GR_SL_KPI_2:** Avg_number_Order lines per hour: Average number of order lines picked per hour.
- **GR_SL_KPI_3:** Avg_MH_for pallet transport_per hour: Average number of Man Hours spent per hour for pallet transport.
- **GR_SL_KPI_4:** Avg_number_Pallets Transported: Average number of pallets transported per hour with the same number of employees.
- **GR_SL_KPI_5:** Avg_number_steps_per hour: Average number of steps per employee per hour for the transportation of boxes/pallets
- **GR_SL_KPI_6:** Avg_number_steps_per hour_docs: Average number of steps per employee per hour for the transportation of documents
- **GR_SL_KPI_7:** AGV_distance_covered: Distance covered by the AGV while performing relevant tasks.
- **GR_SL_KPI_8:** AGV_time_operational: Time during which the AGV was operational performing relevant tasks.
- **GR_SL_KPI_9:** Avg_number_Order lines per hour_SIM: Average number of order lines picked per hour after the optimization of the product location based on the recommendations of the Digital Twin / SIM output.

2) Application KPIs:

- **GR_AL_KPI_1:** Avg_Localization_Error: Measure the average deviation of the AGV location from the target location.
- **GR_AL_KPI_2:** Avg_Map_Generation_Rate: Measure the rate (meters²/sec) at which a map of the warehouse can be created.
- **GR_AL_KPI_3:** Avg_Navigation_Speed: Measure the speed in which the AGV can navigate a specific area (e.g., corridor).
- **GR_AL_KPI_4:** Avg_Follow-me_Human-AGV_Distance_Deviation: Measure the average deviation of the distance between location of the AGV and distance configured by the system when the system is in Follow-Me mode.
- **GR_AL_KPI_5:** Avg>Loading_Time: Measure the average time required by the AGV to get below the load and lift a platform until the AGV is ready to move.
- **GR_AL_KPI_6:** Avg_Unloading_Time: Measure the average time required to unload and escape a load carrying platform.
- **GR_AL_KPI_7:** Avg_E2E_Command_Latency: Measure the average time required for the robot to start an operation when a command is sent.

Figure 36: Grafana measurements: E2E Latency.

- **GR_AL_KPI_8:** Dropped_Packets_Ratio: Dropped packets ratio observed from the application side.
- **GR_AL_KPI_9:** Max_Throughput: Max user experienced throughput observed from the application side.
- **GR_AL_KPI_10_X:** Avg Video Network Latency

Figure 37: Grafana measurements: Video Network Latency.

6. 3rd party onboarding activities

One of the main objectives of the VITAL-5G project is to promote the developed and fully integrated and tested platform to 3rd party experimenters and provide resources coming from the three Use Cases (UCs) of the project and the 3GPP Rel. 16 SA testbeds to enable them to develop their own Network Applications, Vertical Services and experiment with free access. Through the provision of these resources to 3rd party experimenters, we aim to enable innovation in the T&L sector that the project focuses on and through the use of an extensive Network Application catalogue (containing Vertical Specific and Vertical Agnostic Network Applications) and the ability to onboard 3rd party Network Applications with an intuitive and automatic way without the need of prior knowledge in orchestration or backend programming to enable new applications across a variety of sectors. The section below describes the resources available to 3rd parties, the activities that the project planned concerning 3rd parties until M30 and the KPIs achieved so far and our future planning to attract as many 3rd parties as possible and create a VITAL-5G ecosystem, as at M30, the 3rd parties are can fully use the available resources provided by the VITAL-5G.

6.1. Testbed resources available to 3rd party activities

VITAL-5G, has announced the opening of its ground-breaking 5G experimentation infrastructure to foster innovation among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), start-ups, and researchers in the T&L sector. This significant development aims to facilitate the development and testing of novel vertical services tailored specifically for the T&L industry.

To accomplish this ambitious goal, VITAL-5G has established three trial sites, strategically located in Belgium, Romania, and Greece. These trial sites serve as dedicated spaces where interested parties can access cutting-edge resources and conduct extensive experimentation with 5G technology. Furthermore, these trial sites are supported by three 3GPP Rel. 16 SA testbeds, enhancing their capabilities and offering additional resources and expertise to the participants.

The resources provided by the three 5G-PPP testbeds are designed to empower and assist innovators in their pursuit of developing and refining 5G-enabled vertical services for the T&L sector. These resources include but are not limited to:

High-Speed and Low-Latency Connectivity: The testbeds offer access to state-of-the-art 5G network infrastructure, ensuring reliable and high-speed connectivity for participants. The low-latency capabilities of 5G technology enable real-time communication and data transfer, essential for time-sensitive T&L operations.

Network Slicing and Quality of Service (QoS): The testbeds support network slicing, a technology that allows the creation of virtualized networks tailored to specific service requirements. This feature ensures that participants can allocate network resources efficiently and customize their connectivity based on the needs of their vertical services. The quality-of-service guarantees provided by the testbeds ensure reliable and uninterrupted connectivity for mission-critical T&L operations.

Technical Expertise and Support: Alongside the infrastructure, the testbeds offer technical expertise and support from experienced professionals in the field of 5G technology. This assistance aids participants in leveraging the available resources effectively, addressing technical challenges, and maximizing the potential of their vertical service offerings.

By granting access to these resources, VITAL-5G aims to nurture an ecosystem of innovation and collaboration, driving the development of transformative 5G-powered solutions for the T&L sector. The initiative aspires to accelerate the adoption of 5G technology in transportation and logistics, unlocking new opportunities for efficiency, safety, and sustainability in this vital industry.

The assets offered per testbed/trial site can be seen in Figure 38-Figure 40.

Figure 38: Available assets in the Belgian trial site/testbed.

Figure 39: Available assets in the Romanian trial site/testbed.

Figure 40: Available assets in the Greek trial site/testbed.

6.2. 3rd party activities

During the lifetime of the VITAL-5G project, the consortium has been focused on designing activities and implementing a dissemination and communication strategy tailored to attracting 3rd party experimenters and onboarding them on the VITAL-5G platform. This will lead to the project realising its full potential and have significant impact in the European innovation ecosystem by promoting innovation coming from SMEs, start-ups, academia and industrial stakeholders with a focus on T&L stakeholders.

For this reason, the VITAL-5G consortium has organised activities to attract 3rd party experimenters in the form of webinars explaining both the scientific background of Network Applications and demonstrating the capabilities of our facilities, a technical workshop concerning the project's plans for 3rd party engagement and onboarding as well as a Hackathon which attracted more than 20 external stakeholders leading to 3 new ideas being generated and the start of the development of 4 new Network Applications through the use of the VITAL-5G platform.

Concerning external events, the VITAL-5G consortium participated in a number of key events pertaining to the telecommunications and T&L communities such as the Transport Research Arena (TRA) 2022 conference, the IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC) 2023, the 2022 and 2023 EuCNC & 6G Summit, the Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) 2023 to name a few. The participation took the form of both booth exhibitions and participation in special sessions and submission of scientific publications which serve as a means of making the various communities aware of our project and promoting the onboarding of 3rd party experimenters on the VITAL-5G platform and boosting our engagement and driving forward innovation and our goals of a sustainable VITAL-5G ecosystem during and after the lifetime of the project. Another important aspect of the project's outreach strategy is our participation to various fora that could help us attract more 3rd parties on the platform while in parallel tackling our standardisation contribution goals. The partners are participating in various Working Groups (WGs) of 5G-PPP, in ITU and ETSI WGs as well as other organisations such as AIOTI trying to spread our onboarding activities as far as possible. Project partners have also been participating to webinars relevant to our effort of spreading our message such as events organised by ALICE which VITAL-5G has grown a strong connection with. The project has also developed collaborations with other 5G-PPP projects which will help us boost our metrics in terms of engaging thus having greater chances of attracting more potential 3rd party experimenters.

Finally, the VITAL-5G website is continuously updated with material for 3rd party experimenters (e.g., technical information concerning the platform, scientific publications that are available through Zenodo in open access, non-technical publications and dissemination material produced specifically for promoting the platform and the project's assets). The website features a dedicated section to 3rd party experimenters where the experimentation process is detailed and where potential 3rd party experimenters can contact the consortium by filling out a questionnaire constructed in such a way for us to get a working profile of the potential experimenter and directing them to the appropriate technical partners (MNOs, trial site leaders, etc.) and provide the best experience we can.

6.3. KPIs achieved and future planning

Through the efforts described in section 6.2, we have managed to come in contact with 38 parties out of which 13 were innovative SMEs, 11 large companies, 6 research-performing organisations, 5 universities, 2 European Commission-funded projects and 1 telecommunications company. This has been achieved through the collaboration between the consortium partners and with the valuable support coming especially from the project's MNOs and trial sites.

The project's goal of onboarding 30 3rd party experimenters and developing 10 new Network Applications is a rather challenging goal but something that the consortium fights to achieve every day. The challenges to reach this goal are being measured constantly and our strategy is adapted accordingly. At the submission of this deliverable, the project has decided to participate more strategically to external events both with physical and

online presence as well as cultivate all of our acquired connections from previous participation to events to boost our onboarding numbers. Some important lessons learned are that onboarding 3rd parties with no available budget for an open call requires a bigger timescale consideration in the lifecycle and a much bigger effort from the consortium partners. Given all the obstacles inherently present in the execution of the project since the signing of the Grant Agreement, we are happy with our progress and we now know where to strategically focus.

7. Conclusion

The integration of the VITAL-5G platform with its components and the three testbeds has been successfully accomplished, relevant outputs and results being demonstrated by this deliverable. All platform components are operational in the production environment, and their southbound interfaces for monitoring, slicing, and orchestration are seamlessly integrated with the corresponding interfaces of the testbeds.

The three testbeds themselves are integrated at both the 5G RAN/Core and virtualized infrastructure levels with the platform's orchestration, monitoring, and slicing management functions. For the Drop II release of the platform, static slicing capability was made available across all testbeds. Dynamic slicing was introduced in the final Drop III release, enhancing the platform's flexibility and resource allocation capabilities. This is an ongoing effort to be implemented in all testbeds.

The deliverable outputs provide detailed evidence that the requested network upgrades and software implementations have been successfully executed. The integration of VITAL-5G system components aligns with the planned functionality perspective, and extensive platform functional tests demonstrate the operational readiness of the system. It is functioning effectively in a live 5G environment, specifically catering to the Transport & Logistics (T&L) infrastructure, and is fully capable of supporting 3rd party experimenters within an open 5G environment.

The deliverable for Drop III showcases the final integrated system of VITAL-5G, highlighting its operational readiness and presenting the results of extensive validation efforts to ensure functionality. This milestone signifies the delivery of the second full version of the end-to-end VITAL-5G system, which includes Network Applications, an open repository, and supporting tools. This version is now available for comprehensive trial experiments conducted by both internal partners and 3rd-party collaborators.

While the VITAL-5G Platform and the 5G testbeds are currently implemented and ready for 3rd party experimentation in the production environment, ongoing efforts will focus on validating and expanding the system. This includes integrating new features that emerge from development activities in WP2 and from the feedback that will be received by the 3rd party experimenters, aiming to enhance the 5G services provided. Furthermore, any identified bugs, issues, or malfunctions will be diligently reported, investigated, and addressed in the upcoming period, ensuring the continued refinement and stability of the system.

8. References

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